

Influence of source and level of nitrogen application on pest incidence

K. Swaminathan, R. Saroja, and N. Raju, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

In a field experiment, we compared the effect of ammonium chloride and urea N at 50, 100, 150, or 200 kg N/ha on pest incidence in 1983-84 samba.

Thirty-d-old IR20 seedlings were planted in 8- × 6-m plots at 20- × 15-cm

spacing. One-half N was applied basally and one-half in split doses 25 and 45 d after planting (DT). At planting, 22 kg P and 42 kg K/ha were applied. The crop was treated with carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ha 22 DT. The experiment had eight treatments in four replications.

Leaffolder (LF) damage was recorded on 20 hills/plot 60 DT. Gall midge (GM) infestation, number of silvershoots, and number of tillers on 20 hills/plot were recorded at 60 DT. At harvest, number

of whiteheads and productive tillers on 20 hills/plot were recorded to determine stem borer (SB) infestation (see table).

Increasing N application increased LF and SB incidence, but N source did not affect pest population.

GM intensity was greatest at low N application. Urea N plots had significantly higher GM incidence than ammonium chloride plots. All pest incidence was low at the recommended application of 100 kg N/ha. □

Identification of rice leaffolders (LF) by wing markings

A. T. Barrion and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis (Guenée) is the only reported LF pest of rice in the Philippines. Recently, two *Marasmia* species with similar appearance were found to damage rice leaves. We developed an illustrated key (see figure) based on wing markings to identify each species. □

Wing markings of LF in the Philippines.

Effect of N source and level on pest incidence in 1983-84 samba, Tirur, India.

N (kg/ha)	LF damage (%)			GM silvershoots (%)			SB whiteheads (%)		
	Urea	Ammonium chloride	Mean	Urea	Ammonium chloride	Mean	Urea	Ammonium chloride	Mean
50	19	17	18 a	28	24	26 b	23	22	23 a
100	21	21	21 a	23	22	22 a	25	25	25 ab
150	30	28	29 b	20	21	21 a	27	26	27 b
200	40	38	39 c	23	19	21 a	30	29	30 c
Mean	27	26		24 b	21 a		26	26	
CD for source : ns				1.76			ns		
CD for N levels: 3.93				2.49			2.83		
CD for interaction: ns				ns			ns		

Scarabaeid beetle outbreak in upland rice

S. Sharma, Indian Council for Agricultural Research Complex for NEH Region, Nagaland Centre, Medziphema 79106, India

The scarabaeid beetle *Alissonotum simile* Arrow (Coleoptera:Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae) severely damaged (90%) upland rice Nagaland special, a local tall variety around Medziphema in Kohima District in Apr-Jun 1982. This is the first recorded incidence of the scarabaeid beetle in northeastern India. *A. simile*, *A. piceum* (F.) and *A. impressicole* (Arr.) have been recorded in sugarcane fields in Bihar, Assam, and West Bengal where they damage new shoots beneath the soil and cause deadhearts. In severe cases the shoots may be cut.

Both grubs and adults damaged rice, but adult beetles did more harm by cutting young plants just below the soil surface. Rice plants at maximum tillering were heavily attacked. The larvae fed on roots, but caused little damage. □

Influence of water regime on rice whorl maggot oviposition

V. D. Viajante and E. A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, IRRI

Rice plants grown with continuous standing water the first 3-4 wk after transplanting have more *Hydrellia philippina* (RWM) damage than plants in fields where the soil is saturated, but without standing water. We evaluated RWM oviposition on plants in saturated and flooded plots.

Fifteen-day-old IR36 seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing in 6- × 25-m plots. Saturated and flooded treatments were in a randomized complete block design. In flooded plots, water was maintained at a 5-cm depth from transplanting to 25 d after transplanting (DT). There was no standing water in the saturated plots.

RWM flies preferred the flooded plots for oviposition (see table). There were three to six times more eggs in flooded plots than in saturated plots. □